

DEVELOPMENT OF SOLAR SEGWAY VEHICLE

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ABSTRACT

The Segway is a uniquely sophisticated machine that uses on-board computers working with multiple sensors and redundant physical systems to sense the motions of the rider, and to react to those motions. The “Stand up Scooter” requires the rider to learn how the machine will respond to the throttle and brake, while physically holding on to the machine to counter the unbalanced forces of acceleration and deceleration.

KEYWORDS: Develop segway without using complex and electronics parts.

1) INTRODUCTION

The Solar Segway is an innovative mode of personalized transportation that combines renewable energy and modern technology to create a sustainable and eco-friendly option for commuters and adventurers alike. This is a self-balancing personal transportation vehicle that is propelled by electric motors, powered by solar panels, and controlled by intuitive hand and foot movements of the rider. It is an efficient and agile way to travel short to medium distances while reducing your carbon footprint and increasing your overall efficiency. With the Solar Segway, you can enjoy the freedom of mobility while experiencing the joys of sustainable living. Segway is an electric scooter of future technology; it is often used to transport a user across mid-range distances in urban environments. It has more degrees of freedom than car or bike and is faster than pedestrian. They are more efficient than fuel powered vehicles for shorter distance and time of travelling. An electrical vehicle such as Segway, if widely used in the society would give a helping hand in reducing pollutions caused by two wheelers. It would save time and efforts in travelling short distances on barefoot for ages of people.

2) LITERATURE REVIEW

Segway CM Balance Robot Soccer Player Jeremy Sea rock, Brett Browning, Manuela Veloso J seacock May 2004 CMU-CS-03-205 This paper presents the design, fabrication and control of the Segway human transporter; a two-wheeled, self-balancing electric vehicle. We aim at producing a fully-operational Segway vehicle with a compact design which caters for shock absorption on rough terrains and includes an improved control system.

Luis A. Porrell o, Ph.D., P.E. and Michael G. Jones., „A Call for Interest—The Segway Human Transporter”: The article starts off by highlighting how the introduction of the Segway Human Transporter (HT) was highly anticipated, but ended up being viewed as a failure. Despite this, the authors believe that the Segway HT has potential uses in various fields such as tourism, security, and transportation in certain scenarios.

Jeremy Sea rock, Brett Browning, Manuela Veloso „Segway CM Balance Robot Soccer Player“: May 2004 CMU-CS-03-205 School of Computer Science the Robotics Institute Carnegie Mellon University, PA, 15213 The paper titled "Segway CM Balance Robot Soccer Player" was authored by Jeremy Sea rock, Brett Browning, and Manuela Veloso. It was published in May 2004 and the publication comes from the School of Computer Science and the Robotics Institute of Carnegie Mellon University, located in Pennsylvania with a zip code of 15213.

Ji Yeong Lee , Lerrel Joseph Pinto, Dong-Hyung Kim and Chang-Soo Han, Member, IEEE, Development of a Segway Robot for an Intelligent Transport System“, IEEE International Symposium on System Integration Kyushu University, Fukuoka, Japan December 16 to 18, year 2012 ,This paper describes the development and implementation of a Segway robot for an intelligent transport system. The authors discuss the motivation behind the project and the challenges they faced in developing the robot.

Taimoor Tariq, Muhammad Harris Khan, Mehak Chaudhry, Qurat-ul-Ain Fatima, Umer Izhar Department of Mechatronics Engineering National University of Science &Technology, „Fabrication and Modelling of Segway“, Proceedings of 2014 IEEE International Conference on Mechatronics and Automation August 3 to 6, Tianjin, China The paper presents the fabrication and modeling of a Segway vehicle. The Segway is a two-wheeled vehicle that uses feedback control to maintain its balance. The authors describe the design and fabrication of the Segway, including the selection of components and materials.

3) EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

3.1 Block Diagram of the Vehicle.

Fig 3.1.1: - Block Diagram of Solar Segway-Vehicle

3.2 Designed by Using CATIA_V5 Software.

Fig 3.2.1: - Front & Side view of the model

Fig 3.2.2: - Isometric view of the model

These are my 3D models designed by using CATIA_V5, are extensively used to development process of Agri vehicle, due to numerous advantages including accuracy, flexibility, and to ease to modify.

- Created a 3D digital model of the vehicle, incorporating its various components, such as chassis, motor, battery, solar panel, transmission, wheels, cultivators, cutter, fertilizer and Seed Sower.
- The individual components are assembled together to form the complete vehicle assembly has we shown in above figures ensuring that proper fittings and alignment.

3.3 Parts and its Operations.

A. MAIN FRAME

Fig 3.3.1: Mild Steel Frame 25.4mm

1-inch square Mild steel material is used for cultivator frame due to its strength, durability and also relatively low cost.

- By the help of hydraulic press, Bending the steel plates to create angles and curves for structural elements such as the main frame, cross section of the member, and mounting brackets.
- Components in position using clamps or fixtures to maintain alignment during welding.
- Applying surface treatments such as paint to protect the steel against corrosion.

B. MOTORS

Fig 3.3.2: 24v Dc Motor, With 3000rpm

DC Motor is used to perform the operation due to its high torque, speed control, efficiency, and relatively low cost.

- High carbon steel blades offer excellences durability, strength and reliability, suitable for cutting thick or tough grass.
- By carefully fastening each screw, the DC motor is securely affixed to the frame, ready to power the blade attachments with precision and efficiency.

C. WHEELS

Fig 3.3.3: - Wheels

- The wheels used in this project are Scooty wheels of 254mmDAI wheels, we have used 3wheels for this project (2 and 1 small).

D. SOLAR PANEL

Fig 3.3.4: Solar panel

- The solar panel capacity is 12*12V panel, produces 35V electricity. Can be used alternatively also.

E. CHAIN DRIVE

Fig 3.3.5: Chain drive

- Chain drive system is a mechanism that transfers power from the engine to the rear wheel of a scooter through a series of interconnected links.
- The chain drive consists of two sprockets: one on the engine shaft and the other on the rear wheel.
- It is mounted on the back of the chassis between the battery and the motor

F. BATTERY

Fig 3.3.6: Battery 12v, 5000mah

- The battery used for this project is 12v, 5000MAH sealed lead acid battery. We are using 2 numbers of batteries in this project.

4) THEORETICAL CALCULATIONS

4.1 Calculation for Current and voltage: -

- We will use the International System of Units (SI). This is modern metric system that is officially accepted in electrical engineering in the USA.
One of the most important laws of physics is the fundamental Ohm's Law. It states that current through the conductor is directly proportional to applied voltage and is expressed as:

$$I = V / R$$

I – current, measured in amperes (A);

V – applied voltage, measured in volts (V);

R – resistance, measured in ohms (Ω).

$$I = 12 / R$$

$$R = 12 / 1.2$$

$$R = 10 \text{ Ohms}$$

This formula could be used in many cases.

- You may calculate the resistance of your motor by measuring the consumed current and applied voltage. For any given resistance (in the motors it is basically the resistance of the coil) this formula explains that the current can be controlled by applied voltage.

The consumed electrical power of the motor is defined by the following formula:

4.2 Calculation for $P_{in} = I * V$

$$P_{in} = 12 * 12$$

$$P_{in} = 144 \text{ w}$$

where P_{in} – input power, measured in watts (W);

I – current, measured in amperes (A);

V – applied voltage, measured in volts (V).

4.3 Calculation of P_{out}

- Motors supposed to do some work and two important values define how powerful the motor is. It is motor speed and torque – the turning force of the motor. Output mechanical power of the motor could be calculated by using the following formula:

$$P_{out} = \tau$$

$$* \omega P_{out} = 18.5$$

$$* \omega \omega = ?$$

where P_{out} – output power, measured in watts (W);

τ – torque, measured in Newton meters (N•m);

ω – angular speed, measured in radians per second (rad/s).

$$\omega = \text{rpm} *$$

$$2\pi / 300 \omega = 63 *$$

$$2\pi / 300 \underline{\omega} =$$

$$\underline{1.3188 \text{ rad/s}}$$

therefore

$$P_{out} = 18.5 * \underline{1.3188}$$

$$P_{out} = 24.39 \text{ W}$$

where ω – angular speed, measured in radians per second (rad/s);

rpm – rotational speed in revolutions per minute;

π – mathematical constant pi (3.14).

60 – number of seconds in a minute

4.3 Calculation of Efficiency:

Efficiency of the motor is calculated as mechanical output power divided by electrical input power:

$$E = P_{out} / P_{in}$$

Therefore, after substitution we get,

$$P_{out} =$$

$$P_{in} * E$$

$$P_{out} / P_{in} = E$$

$$24.39 / 144$$

$$E = .1694 * 100$$

$$E = \underline{16.9 \%}$$

4.4 Calculation for Solar Panel: -

Using 12V, 20watts Solar panel to charge the 12V, 7.5Ah battery.

a) Solar panel output

Considering 80% efficiency

$$20\text{watts} * 0.80 = 16\text{watts}$$

b) Charging rate

$$P = V I$$

Where,

V = Voltage in volts

P = Power in watt

I = Current in amps

$$P = V * I$$

$$16 = 12 * I$$

$$I = 1.33\text{A}$$

c) Charging time

$$\text{Time} = \text{Battery capacity} / \text{Charging current}$$

$$= 7.5 / 1.33$$

$$\text{Charging time} = 5.63 \text{ hrs}$$

5) RESULT AND DISCUSSION

SL. No	Description	Result
1	Time required to turn on	0.45secs
2	Speed	25-30kmph
3	weight	85 kgs max
4	To charge the Battey by using solar panel	5.63

6) CONCLUSION

This project entitled “DEVELOPMENT OF SOLAR SEGWAY VEHICLE” is successfully completed and results obtained is satisfactory. Based on overall performance we can definitely say that the project will satisfy industries, malls & colleges. A solar Segway is a great alternative to cars or other vehicles that consume fossil fuels. It uses clean and renewable energy, which is good for the environment. A solar Segway can be used for sightseeing or tourism purposes. It offers a fun and unique way to explore cities, parks, or other attractions. A solar Segway can be used by security personnel to patrol large areas like parking lots or parks. It allows them to cover more ground in a shorter time and respond quickly to any incidents.

7) ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We consider ourselves proud to be a part of **REVA University** family, the institution which stood by our way in all our endeavors. We express our sincere thanks to **Dr. K S Narayanaswamy** Director and Professor, School of Mechanical Engineering, for his support and encouragement. We express profound thanks to **Prof. Avinash S** Associate Professor, School of Mechanical Engineering, for his valuable support & for his inspiration, guidance, constant supervision, direction and discussions in successful completion of this project.

We are thankful to the project coordinator's, teaching and non-teaching staff members of School of Mechanical Engineering for their co-operation extended towards this work. Finally, we express ourselves heartfelt gratitude to our parents, members of our family and our friends, for their constant support, motivation and encouragement throughout this project. Above all we would like to thank God, Almighty, for having showered his blessings on us.

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